

Mapping Scholarly Identities: A Descriptive Study of Spanish ORCID Records at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

Bruno Penadés¹, Teresa Muñoz-Écija^{2*}, Benjamín Vargas-Quesada³, and Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez¹

bruno.penades@csic.es; teresamunoz@ugr.es; benjamin@ugr.es; zaida.chinchilla@csic.es
0000-0001-7261-6400; 0000-0003-1311-0471; 0000-0001-5115-7460; 0000-0002-1608-4478

¹Institute of Public Goods and Policies (IPP), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Madrid, Spain

²Arqus European University Alliance, University of Granada, Granada, Spain

³Unit for Computational Humanities and Social Sciences (U-CHASS), University of Granada, Granada, Spain.

*Corresponding author

Abstract

This study analyzes the adoption and use of ORCID compared to other researcher profile systems across research domains and job categories at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The sample consists of authors affiliated with CSIC who published at least one publication between 2013 and 2022. The results reveal that the adoption rate of ORCID was higher than for public Google Scholar profiles. The ORCID profiles show a gender gap, with men registering more profiles and completing more fields. Permanent researchers adopted ORCID to a greater extent and were among those who completed the most sections. Natural Resources and Social Science had the highest profile number, while Humanities displayed the most complete profiles. In addition, a rapid increase in ORCID registrations was observed in the early years following its implementation, followed by a gradual decline, while ORCID profile updates remained consistent over time. We hope our findings could inform researchers and institutional strategies to enhance the use of persistent identifiers, strengthen data completeness, and address the gender gap in ORCID adoption, ultimately supporting the CSIC's commitment to open science and research integrity.

Keywords: ORCID adoption, ORCID completeness, gender, job category, thematic area, CSIC.

Key Points

- The creation of ORCID profiles experienced rapid growth following the emergence of the organization, which gradually declined after peaking in 2014.
- The percentage of authors who adopted ORCID was moderate (63.8%), but higher than Google Scholar public profiles and the percentages of active fields was low (38.6%).

- 35 ● There is a gender gap, with men having more registrations (Male: 69.9%; Female:
36 57.9%) and more active fields completed in their profiles (Male: 40.1%; Female:
37 36.9%).
- 38 ● Permanent researchers adopted ORCID at a higher rate (86.8%) and were who
39 completed more fields (40.6%), while the areas with the most registrations were Natural
40 Resources (72.6%) and Social Sciences (72.4%), and the most complete profiles were
41 found in Humanities (43.7%).
- 42 ● All permanent researchers occupy the top positions in ORCID adoption across research
43 areas, but the number of active fields varied considerably across different job categories
44 within CSIC.
- 45 ● Update of ORCID profiles are consistent over time.

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47 **1. Introduction**

48 The increasing volume of scientific output has underscored the need for mechanisms that ensure
49 the unambiguous identification of authors, preventing attribution errors and enhancing research
50 visibility. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) have emerged as fundamental tools in modern research
51 ecosystems, enabling the seamless connection of researchers' contribution across disciplines,
52 institutions, and time. These identifiers play a crucial role in improving research integrity,
53 ensuring proper attribution, and supporting the principles of open science (Marín-Arraiza,
54 2019).

55 ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is one of the most widely adopted PIDs,
56 providing a unique identifier for researchers and facilitating interoperability among research
57 platforms (Haak et al., 2012). Among the various benefits introduced by this identifier, one of
58 the key advantages of ORCID is its ability to address issues of name ambiguity, which is
59 particularly relevant in regions with common surnames, such as China (Xu & Hu, 2024). It also
60 enables the tracking of various researcher attributes, including institutional affiliations, research
61 output, and professional activities, ensuring accurate and comprehensive scholarly records
62 (Kim, 2025).

63 The adoption of ORCID is also instrumental in increasing research visibility, especially when it
64 is integrated with platforms and researcher profile systems such as ResearchGate, Google
65 Scholar, and Academia.edu (Craft, 2020). These integrations enhance research dissemination,
66 foster academic networking (Fernández-Ramos & Barrionuevo, 2021), and support the
67 evaluation of research outputs (Boudry & Durand-Barthez, 2020).

68 Beyond visibility, ORCID makes a significant contribution to research transparency, integrity,
69 and credibility. It improves the tracking of scholarly outputs, even in cases of group authorship
70 or when retractions must be incorporated into researcher profiles (Candal-Pedreira et al., 2024).
71 ORCID also plays a role in addressing academic integrity challenges, such as combating journal
72 hijacking on indexing platforms like Scopus (Abalkina, 2024). Furthermore, ORCID is part of
73 the infrastructure employed in initiatives like the standardized 'Publication Facts Label', which
74 provides critical metadata on the publication process and helps researchers and readers assess
75 the reliability of academic work (Willinsky & Pimentel, 2024).

76 Despite the growing use of ORCID and its recognized benefits for scholarly communication,
77 there has been no comprehensive analysis of its adoption within Spain's largest research
78 institution, the Spanish National Research Council. In particular, little is known about how
79 CSIC researchers use ORCID about other profile systems, the completeness of their records, or
80 patterns linked to gender, job category, and research domains. This study addresses that gap by
81 examining the adoption and use of ORCID among CSIC-affiliated authors, aiming to provide a
82 detailed overview of usage trends, metadata quality, and demographic differences.

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84 **1.1 Literature review**

85 Among the various systems that support open science communication, ORCID stands out due to
86 its broad adoption and integration into scholarly infrastructure. It enables researchers to
87 consolidate information related to their publications, funded projects, and academic
88 collaborations, offering a persistent digital identity (Haak et al., 2012). Nevertheless, enhancing
89 metadata completeness and interoperability among platforms remains a significant challenge for
90 managing research output. In this context, a comparison between ORCID and repositories such
91 as DataCite, Zenodo, Dryad, and Figshare highlights DataCite's central role in facilitating cross-
92 platform data exchange (Sixto-Costoya et al., 2021).

93 The integration of OpenAlex with ORCID has further improved academic record accuracy for
94 Spanish researchers, expanding metadata coverage and strengthening research tracking
95 mechanisms (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025). In the US and Canada, academic librarians have
96 emphasized ORCID's priority over other platforms and recommended its broader adoption in
97 research institutions (Zhang & Kumaran, 2022; Fuhr & Monnin, 2024). However, metadata
98 completeness remains with some gaps, as missing ORCID IDs for some researchers and
99 insufficient standardization hinder the full potential of persistent identifiers in research
100 assessment (Aghassibake et al., 2023; Costas et al., 2024).

101 National and institutional initiatives have leveraged PIDs to enhance research management,
102 reduce administrative burdens, and align with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible,
103 Interoperable, and Reusable) (Cousijn et al., 2021; Marín- Arraiza, 2022). In Germany, ORCID
104 has been adopted to streamline research administration (Pampel et al., 2024), while institutions
105 such as Université Grenoble Alpes have emphasized their role in assessing research
106 performance, institutional visibility, and open science policies (Larrieu et al., 2024). The global
107 adoption of ORCID has improved metadata management, affiliation tracking, and research
108 accessibility (Fernández-Marcial et al., 2023; Heusse & Cabanac, 2022; Quinn, 2023; Calvo &
109 Arquero Avilés, 2020).

110 Beyond this role in research administration, ORCID is also a tool that provides valuable insights
111 into scientific mobility, revealing research trajectories and their implications for science and
112 migration policies (Moreno-Delgado et al., 2024). It helps identify patterns in global
113 collaboration, including regionalization trends and the stability of scientific partnerships
114 (Gomez et al., 2020; Porter, 2022). In addition, ORCID data from the US has demonstrated that
115 mobility trends are influenced by institutional prestige and research intensity, though disparities
116 persist based on geographical location and gender (Hannak et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2020).

117 While ORCID has been widely adopted by research institutions, its implementation faces
118 significant challenges. Ethical concerns regarding mandatory implementation, data protection,
119 and academic autonomy have been noted, particularly in studies examining attitudes in Irish
120 higher education (Houghton & Foster, 2024; Teixeira da Silva, 2020). Adoption rates also vary
121 across institutional roles, with librarians and administrative staff often embracing ORCID at
122 higher rates than academic researchers, though many scholars acknowledge the benefits
123 outweigh the potential risks (Teixeira da Silva, 2024).

124 In Spain, the integration of ORCID into research institutions began in 2013 at the University of
125 Oviedo, followed by efforts from the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)
126 to promote its national adoption (Marín-Arraiza & Mejias, 2020). The Spanish National
127 Research Council, the country's largest public research institution, subsequently incorporated
128 ORCID into its research management infrastructure. As a member of the ORCID consortium,
129 CSIC has developed several systems to support ORCID integration, including GesBIB, a
130 bibliometric database for analyzing scientific output and impact. The institutional adoption of
131 ORCID has facilitated seamless interactions between ORCID IDs and CSIC's internal research
132 information systems, enabling federated authentication and automatic publication data
133 synchronization with researcher profiles (Dorado, 2019).

134 Even with these initiatives, no comprehensive study has examined ORCID adoption among
135 CSIC researchers, particularly with bibliographic database profiles and usage patterns.
136 Therefore, the objectives of this study are (1) to assess ORCID adoption compared to other
137 researcher profile systems; (2) to analyze whether job category and research area influence
138 ORCID adoption and participation; (3) to evaluate the activation of ORCID metadata fields; and
139 (4) to examine trends in record completeness and profile update frequency. Additionally, all
140 analyses will incorporate a gender perspective, focusing on authors affiliated with CSIC who
141 have published at least once between 2013 and 2022.

142 We hope this study serves as an empirical reference for future actions that CSIC may take to
143 improve the adoption and completion of researchers' profiles. The findings could inform
144 institutional strategies to enhance the use of persistent identifiers, strengthen data completeness,
145 and address the gender gap in ORCID adoption, thus supporting the CSIC's commitment to
146 open science and research integrity.

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148 **2. Methods**

149 **2.1 Data collection**

150 This study relies on data extracted from GesBIB and other CSIC databases related to job
151 category and ORCID, two complementary sources for analyzing researcher profiles. GesBIB is
152 a bibliographic and scientific publication management platform developed by CSIC. From this
153 source, researcher-level information was gathered, including persistent author identifiers
154 (Scopus Author ID, owned by Elsevier; ResearcherID, owned by Clarivate Analytics; and
155 ORCID ID), academic public profiles (Google Scholar Profile), job positions within CSIC from
156 the GESPER CSIC database, and the institutional affiliations from which authors had published.
157 In addition, ORCID data were taken from the previous study by Arroyo-Machado et al. (2025),
158 providing a continuation of the analysis of Spanish researchers' presence on this platform.

159 **2.2 Sample selection**

160 The initial dataset included 13,847 authors (Female: 51%; Male: 49%) who published at least
161 one publication between 2013 and 2022. Duplicate records (n=3; 0.02%) and those without any
162 employment data (n=21; 0.2%) were removed.

163 **2.2.1 Job categories**

164 GesBIB is enriched by the GESPER platform, which registers the job category of authors
165 affiliated with the CSIC, including three variables intended to record the job positions of CSIC
166 staff. The job scale variable contained 93 non-standardized job categories (missing values:
167 2.5%). Additionally, a second variable recoded job types, which included 40 categories (missing
168 values: 0.3%). The third variable, namely job subtypology contained the same amount of data,
169 but with very generic labels. To ensure data consistency, all missing values in the job category
170 variable were reclassified by cross-checking the information available for each of the three
171 reference periods, using any recorded job category to assign the most accurate classification. As
172 a result, no missing values remain in the final dataset.

173 Permanent researchers were composed of tenured scientists, research scientists, research
174 professors, and, to a lesser extent, ad honorem and distinguished researchers. Temporary staff
175 included all fellows, visiting researchers, employees hired under a specific project, among
176 others. Support staff consisted mainly of technicians, who could be either temporary or
177 permanent, as well as members of the state administration.

178 Temporary staff constituted the vast majority of CSIC authors and was the category with the
179 highest gender parity (Fig. 1). Permanent researchers represented a much smaller percentage,
180 and the proportion of men significantly exceeded that of women, unlike support staff, where
181 women were in the majority, despite being the staff category with the fewest authorship
182 contributions.

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184 **Figure 1.** Percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors by job category and gender

185 **2.2.2 Research areas**

186 The CSIC comprises over 120 research institutes, with its research structured into three broad
187 areas: Life, Matter, and Society (Table 1). These areas encompass eight specific research
188 domains: Life: Agricultural Sciences, Biology and Biomedicine, Food Science and Technology,
189 and Natural Resources; Matter: Chemical Science and Technologies, Materials Science and

190 Technology, and Physical Science and Technologies; and Society: Humanities and Social
191 Sciences.

Research area	Research domain
Life	- Agricultural Sciences - Biology and Biomedicine - Food Science and Technology - Natural Resources
Matter	- Chemical Science and Technologies - Materials Science and Technology - Physical Science and Technologies
Society	- Humanities and Social Sciences

192 **Table 1.** CSIC research areas and research domains

193 The database included two variables identifying the last CSIC center or institute from which
194 authors were affiliated when they published, as well as a variable listing all the institutes where
195 authors had been affiliated, in the case of multiple affiliations.

196 We recoded all centers or institutes into their respective research areas, and we separated
197 Humanities from Social Sciences. Although both research domains share many similarities, the
198 main reason for dividing them was the distinct methodological approaches used in each to
199 address their respective study objects.

200 Furthermore, the database not only includes research centers or institutes but also presidents,
201 vice-presidents, and delegations, which were recoded into the research area corresponding to the
202 institution with which each author was affiliated at the time of publication. To ensure accuracy,
203 we accessed the researchers' profiles in GesBIB database to retrieve relevant information.
204 Additionally, variables were combined to cross-check data when coding discrepancies arose,
205 minimizing the loss of information, including the minimal initial missing values (0.2%).

206 Biology and Biomedicine represented the research domain with the greatest number of authors
207 at the CSIC and a large proportion of women (Fig. 2). In contrast, Physical Sciences and
208 Technologies displayed the greatest gender disparity, favoring men, and were the third-largest
209 area in terms of publishing researchers. Agricultural Sciences closely followed, with women
210 making similar contributions to Biology and Biomedicine. However, the highest visibility of
211 female authors was found in Food Science and Technology, despite it being one of the research
212 domains with the fewest publishing staff. Humanities and Social Sciences, although the smallest
213 domain, exhibited a more balanced gender distribution.

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Figure 2. Percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors by research domains and gender

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2.2.3 Matching procedure with ORCID and the number of active fields

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Records from GesBIB were linked to ORCID metadata via ORCID ID from the orcid_metrics.csv file previously used in a study intended to analyze ORCID's patterns among Spanish researchers (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025). After matching the sample was reduced to 7,193 authors (Male: 54.2%; Female: 45.8%). 18.5% of cases with ORCID were not merged with the data from orcid_metrics.csv due to their absence in the file. The distribution of these cases by gender (Male: 51.3%; Female: 48.7%) and job category (Temporary Staff: 77.7%; Permanent Researchers: 15%; Support Staff: 7.2%) was random. Only 3 cases (0.04%) were removed after the merge because they contained NULL values in the descriptive information.

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ORCID adoption was measured as the proportion of researchers with an ORCID ID. Additionally, adoption/indexing rates for other researcher profile systems (Scopus Author ID, ResearcherID, and Google Scholar Profile) included in GesBIB, were processed. Scopus Author IDs and ResearcherIDs are generated automatically when an author has works indexed in those services; therefore, their presence reflects indexing practices as much as individual 'adoption' Google Scholar Profiles refer to those explicitly created by researchers, not to the inclusion of works in Google Scholar. In the case of the CSIC, we assume that ORCID ID is actively obtained and registered by the researcher. Then, ORCID CSIC's integration (through GesBIB/URICI) allows updates to the 'Works' field in ORCID when researchers authorize the connection; CSIC does not post other metadata (e.g., funding, service activities) on behalf of researchers (Dorado, 2019). This clarification highlights the conceptual difference between automatically assigned identifiers and voluntary adoption, and completeness of active fields in ORCID.

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Profile completeness was assessed as the percentage of active fields in the ORCID record – that is, the proportion of the 13 ORCID metadata fields, excluding the name field, as it is a basic requirement for account creation (ORCID, 2025). Descriptive analyses were conducted to examine ORCID adoption and the number of active fields across job categories, research areas, and gender. Metadata fields were analyzed to determine common completion patterns, intersections between fields, and profile update frequencies. Statistical analyses were carried out using R (v4.5.1).

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246 3. Results

247 3.1 Adoption of researcher profile systems

248 The 13,847 CSIC-affiliated authors who, published at least once between 2013 and 2022, had at
249 least one persistent identifier or author profile on the main academic platforms (99.5%; Fig. 3).
250 As Scopus IDs and Researcher IDs are auto-assigned, most CSIC-affiliated authors have a
251 profile in each system. Both authors' profiles show equal proportions by gender. Therefore, their
252 presence does not necessarily reflect an active choice by the researcher in the same way as
253 ORCID registration. In contrast, the open and independent ORCID identifier lagged far behind,
254 with men using it more frequently than women by over ten percentage points.

255 Among researchers without an ORCID profile but with a Scopus Author ID, women were
256 overrepresented (Female: 59.5%; Male: 40.5%), as well as temporary staff (Temporary Staff:
257 80.3%; Support Staff: 14.1%; Permanent Researchers: 5.6%). The same proportions were
258 observed among those holding a Researcher ID without an ORCID. Figures 4 and 5 show the
259 distribution of job category, gender and research areas among researchers with and without an
260 ORCID profile

261 Another specific case was the public academic profiles offered by Google Scholar. Not only
262 were a minority of CSIC-affiliated authors registered, but the largest gender gap was also
263 observed.

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265 **Figure 3.** Percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors with researcher profiles by gender. **Note:** Total
266 percentages are presented alongside the name of the researcher profile system.

267 3.2 ORCID adoption and completeness by job category

268 The degree of adoption and completeness varied considerably among the different employment
269 categories within CSIC (Fig. 4). Permanent researchers had the highest ORCID adoption rates
270 (86.8%) and also the highest completeness levels (40.6%), with minimal gender differences in
271 either direction. In contrast, the lowest adoption percentage was observed among support staff
272 (39.6%), where women registered lower values than men in both adoption and number of active
273 fields (34.4%).

274 Furthermore, the largest gender gap in adoption was found among temporary staff (Male:
 275 67.8%; Female: 56.6%), and in completeness among support staff (Male: 37.6%; Female:
 276 31.9%).

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278 **Figure 4.** Percentage of ORCID adoption and percentages of active fields among CSIC-
 279 affiliated authors by job category. **Note:** Circles represent female authors and triangles represent
 280 male authors. Colors indicate different job categories. Marker size corresponds to the number of
 281 authors within each job category. Abbreviations are as follows: Perm. Reser. = Permanent
 282 Researchers; Temp. Staff = Temporary Staff; Supp. Staff = Support Staff.

283 3.3 ORCID adoption and completeness by research area

284 This analysis revealed a scenario in which the highest ORCID adoption rates were found in
 285 Natural Resources (72.6%) and Social Sciences (72.4%; Fig. 5). The adoption percentage
 286 decreased gradually across other research domains, with Biology and Biomedicine researchers
 287 at the lowest end (54.9%). The commitment from the Humanities domain was higher than the
 288 other research domains (43.7%), with women standing out, though still far from 50%
 289 completeness. On the other hand, researchers in Biology and Biomedicine had the least
 290 complete profiles (36.7%).

291 In general, women adopted ORCID less frequently than men across all research areas, but it was
 292 in Biology and Biomedicine where less than half of the women had this identifier and where the
 293 engagement levels were the lowest.

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295 **Figure 5.** Distribution of ORCID adoption and completeness among CSIC-affiliated authors by
 296 research domain. **Note:** Circles represent female authors and triangles represent male authors.
 297 Marker size corresponds to the number of authors within each research domain. Colors indicate
 298 different research domains. Abbreviations are as follows: NR = Natural Resources; SS = Social
 299 Sciences; PS&T = Physical Science and Technologies; MS&T = Materials Science and
 300 Technology; H = Humanities; AS = Agricultural Sciences; CS&T = Chemical Science &
 301 Technologies; FS&T = Food Science and Technology; B&B = Biology and Biomedicine.

302 3.4 ORCID adoption and completeness by interaction

303 At this point, we asked whether the effect of job category and research domain, separately,
 304 would interact with the creation of ORCID profiles and the completeness of metadata (Fig. 6).
 305 Permanent researchers in the Physical Sciences were the professionals with the highest ORCID
 306 adoption rates (89.4%). In addition, permanent female researchers in several life science areas
 307 slightly exceeded 90% adoption, as did male social scientists in this employment category.
 308 Meanwhile, the lowest ORCID adoption levels were observed among support staff in Food
 309 Science (29.2%), where women had the fewest researcher profiles.

310 Temporary staff in the Humanities had the highest completion rates (46.8%). Conversely,
 311 support staff in Physical Sciences (30.8%) were at the bottom, although it was the female

312 support staff in Materials Science who had the least complete profiles.

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314 **Figure 6.** Distribution of ORCID adoption and completeness among CSIC-affiliated authors by
 315 job category and research domain. **Note:** Circles represent female authors and triangles
 316 represent male authors. Colors indicate different job categories. Marker size corresponds to the
 317 number of authors within each research domain. Abbreviations are as follows: NR = Natural
 318 Resources; SS = Social Sciences; PS&T = Physical Science and Technologies; MS&T =
 319 Materials Science and Technology; H = Humanities; AS = Agricultural Sciences; CS&T =
 320 Chemical Science & Technologies; FS&T = Food Science and Technology; B&B = Biology
 321 and Biomedicine.

322 A particular case was observed with Biology and Biomedicine, the domain with the most CSIC-
 323 affiliated authors, which showed the lowest adoption and completeness metadata of ORCID
 324 profiles among women (Fig. 5). However, nearly all permanent female researchers, as well as
 325 the majority of temporary ones, had adopted this persistent identifier. Specifically, support staff,
 326 followed by temporary staff, negatively influenced the average result.

327 3.5 Completeness of ORCID metadata

328 The sample was reduced to 7,193 CSIC-affiliated authors, presenting a low number of active
 329 fields in ORCID, (Average active field: 38.6%;. Male: 40.1%; Female: 36.9%). This low
 330 percentage of completed fields can be attributed to a preference for certain specific fields (Fig.
 331 7). Almost all CSIC-affiliated authors included 'Works' (articles in scientific journals, books,
 332 book chapters, etc.). More than twenty percentage points below, the 'Employment' and 'Other

333 IDs' fields were filled out, in equal proportions. Just over half of the researchers entered
 334 'Education and Qualification', while the remaining fields were filled by a minority. Although all
 335 metadata fields were adopted by more men than women, no significant gender differences were
 336 observed. The fields with the greatest disparity were 'Websites and Social Links', 'Peer Review',
 337 and 'Country'.

338 **Figure 7.** Active ORCID fields among CSIC-affiliated authors by gender (percentage of records
 339 with at least one value in each ORCID metadata field). **Note:** Total percentages are shown next
 340 to each field name.
 341

342 Another perspective that helps understand how CSIC-affiliated authors interact with their
 343 ORCID record is by visualizing which fields were active simultaneously (Fig. 8). In this regard,
 344 we found that the three most common intersections were 'Works' and 'Other IDs' (5.2%),
 345 followed by the four fields that the majority of researchers had active (4.9%), and, as the only
 346 additional field, 'Works' (4.6%). We discovered that the tenth intersection corresponded to all
 347 inactive fields (1.9%; Female: 54.5%; Male: 45.5%). That is, researchers who created the
 348 ORCID ID without completing any fields, and very few completed all fields (0.2%; Male:

349 57.1%; Female: 42.9%). The gender distribution of intersections was similar or fluctuated
 350 slightly, except for some specific cases that were among the least frequent intersections.

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352 **Figure 8.** Top 20 metadata field intersections in ORCID records of CSIC-affiliated authors by
 353 gender. **Note:** The three least active fields are not shown due to the absence of intersections
 354 within the top 20.

355 3.6 ORCID registration and profile updating

356 The registration of ORCID identifiers experienced rapid growth since its introduction, peaking
 357 in 2014, before gradually decreasing in subsequent years (Fig. 9A). A pattern of behavior varied
 358 by gender. Men began adopting ORCID identifiers more extensively than women, particularly
 359 in 2012, when the identifier was introduced, and the following year. Later, the creation process
 360 balanced out between genders, although men still stood out, and it wasn't until the last years of
 361 the study period that the creation process tilted slightly in favor of women.

362 When we focus on updating the ORCID records, analyzed with 1,391 CSIC-affiliated authors,
 363 we found that they updated their records frequently, with no significant gender differences (Fig.
 364 9B). The vast majority updated their accounts within less than a year (77.4%). This behavior
 365 was independent of the creation date (Fig. 9C), as CSIC-affiliated authors updated their
 366 accounts within a year. Only slight differences were observed in dispersion according to gender
 367 due to relatively small sample sizes and the presence of authors who took much longer to update
 368 their accounts, appearing as outliers and extreme values.

369

370 **Figure 9.** Distribution of CSIC-affiliated authors' ORCID records by gender and by (A)
 371 creation date, (B) years since last update, and (C) years since last update per creation
 372 date

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374 4. Discussion

375 The results indicate that Scopus Author ID and Researcher ID are the most popular author
 376 identifiers among the CSIC scientific community. Almost all affiliated authors have both
 377 identifiers, while ORCID is far from reaching the same levels. This difference can be easily
 378 explained by the automatic generation of those identifiers when researchers publish in journals
 379 indexed in Scopus and, until 2019, in Web of Science or perhaps also, in part, by the rejection
 380 of the mandatory use of ORCID by some publishers (Teixeira da Silva, 2020; Choraś &
 381 Jaroszewska-Choraś, 2020; Porter, 2022; Teixeira da Silva, 2024). In practical terms, Scopus
 382 Author IDs are automatically created when an author has two or more works indexed in Scopus.
 383 In contrast, for Web of Science, researchers may voluntarily register for a ResearcherID even
 384 without indexed works, although a ResearcherID is also created automatically when an author
 385 has works indexed in Web of Science. The Scopus identifier is much more common in certain
 386 North American universities (Fuhr & Monnin, 2024; Morgan & Eichenlaub, 2018) and even in
 387 Google Scholar Profiles compared to ORCID (Zhang & Li, 2020). However, this percentage
 388 ranking is not constant across other universities and countries, where ORCID represents the

389 most frequent identifier (Boudry & Bouchard, 2025; Tran & Lyon, 2017). Nevertheless, the
390 percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors with an ORCID ID exceeds 60%, which is much higher
391 than the estimate by Porter (2022), who found that fewer than half of active Spanish researchers
392 had an ORCID record by 2019.

393 Another point worth noting is the observed gender gap in both ORCID and Google Scholar
394 Profile identifiers, two platforms that require manual account creation. This is a relatively
395 understudied phenomenon, though it had already been observed among researchers at the
396 University of Caen Normandy (France), where men had more ORCID registrations (Boudry &
397 Durand-Barthez, 2020).

398 Not all CSIC staff responded similarly to the adoption of identifiers. Permanent researchers
399 have embraced ORCID with percentages close to 90%. The majority of temporary staff also had
400 an ORCID. These researchers tend to publish more regularly, and many may have felt
401 compelled to create a profile due to journal policies or funding agencies requiring or promoting
402 the use of ORCID (Choraś & Jaroszewska-Choraś, 2020). These findings align with those of
403 researchers in Toulouse, where ORCID adoption was higher among researchers than professors,
404 and professors more than support staff (Heusse & Cabanac, 2022), among other examples (Fuhr
405 & Monnin, 2024; Zhang & Li, 2020).

406 It is particularly noteworthy that three-quarters of CSIC personnel who published at least once
407 during the study period are made up of temporary staff. Fellows, project-based employees,
408 visiting researchers, etc., remain at the institution only for limited periods, while new PhD
409 candidates and collaborators entered throughout the decade. These CSIC-affiliated authors
410 publish less frequently than permanent researchers and they have fewer ORCID IDs. Still, they
411 were overrepresented in our sample, which may explain why the average adoption rate of
412 ORCID was moderate among CSIC personnel. Moreover, the position of each research domain
413 in terms of ORCID adoption contrasts with findings from other studies. While our sample
414 shows Social Sciences and Humanities in the upper and middle ranks, respectively, several
415 studies have reported the opposite (Boudry & Bouchard, 2025; Boudry & Durand-Barthez,
416 2020; Fuhr & Monnin, 2024; Heusse & Cabanac, 2022). One example is the field of Chemistry,
417 which had one of the highest ORCID adoption rates in aggregated data from various countries,
418 including Spain, in Porter's study (2022). However, in our sample, it ranked among the lowest.
419 ORCID adoption in the CSIC research domains studied exceeds the average percentages
420 observed in each domain across all countries (Porter, 2022). These discrepancies may be due not
421 only to country-specific particularities but also to the criteria used to select the sample and the
422 operationalization of theoretical concepts, which differed in our study compared to Porter's
423 (2022).

424 The same reasoning applies to completion percentages as estimated by Porter (2022), where
425 Spain exceeded 50%, but in our sample, it did not even reach 40%. Nonetheless, Porter
426 documented that the Humanities had high participation rates, which is also evident in the
427 ORCID record completion rates of our sample. Specifically, our results identified that
428 temporary staff in the Humanities were more committed to filling in their ORCID profiles than
429 other professionals.

430 In general, CSIC staff use ORCID IDs to identify their scientific output, demonstrate their
431 professional and educational background, and link their profiles to various academic databases

432 and platforms via other identifiers. This was also observed in a sample of Spanish researchers
433 with ORCID IDs (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025), although the main intersections varied
434 slightly. CSIC-affiliated authors complete roughly the same ORCID fields as the overall
435 Spanish cohort, but they indeed leave most fields inactive. This conclusion was also reached by
436 Fernández-Marcial et al. (2023) after studying at the Faculty of Arts and Humanities at the
437 University of Porto. A significant portion of professors filled in 'Works', 'Employment', and
438 'Education and Qualification' fields, but biographical information (such as the 'Biography',
439 'Country', and 'Keywords' fields) was scarce, which contributes to the identification of profiles
440 in a unique manner.

441 On the other hand, the growth curve we observed in ORCID registration during the study period
442 is consistent with the Spanish researcher sample (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025; Porter, 2022),
443 although not all countries followed the same growth pattern (Porter, 2022). The time since the
444 last update is shorter among CSIC-affiliated authors than in the Spanish sample with ORCID
445 profiles (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025). This could be because the public institution can update
446 the ORCID profiles if the owner authorizes it (Dorado, 2019).

447 **5. Limitations and further studies**

448 Despite the insights gained from our sample, the study was not without limitations.

449 The effect of starting with a moderate percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors with ORCID IDs
450 and, at the same time, almost 20% not matching the identifiers from the Spanish researchers'
451 metadata, resulted in a significant reduction in the sample size when analyzing the interaction
452 between job category and research domains. This also became evident in analyses on the time
453 elapsed since ORCID profiles were updated.

454 Up until now, studies on ORCID adoption and/or completion that include gender have been
455 rare. More examples from other scientific institutions need to be documented to determine
456 whether CSIC is an isolated case or part of a broader trend. Moreover, the number of
457 publications by researchers might be a substantial explanatory factor. Future research will aim
458 to increase the number of publications from CSIC-affiliated authors to narrow the sample to
459 CSIC employees with research profiles.

460 In addition, the dataset used in this study (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025) does not include
461 information on whether ORCID record updates were made manually by researchers or
462 automatically through third-party integrations (e.g., publishers, Crossref, or DataCite).
463 Distinguishing between these modes of update would offer valuable insight into researchers'
464 actual engagement with ORCID and the extent to which they rely on automated mechanisms —
465 an aspect that should be addressed in future studies

466 **6. Conclusions**

467 The CSIC has adopted specific policies to encourage ORCID, however, our results show that
468 the percentage of CSIC-affiliated authors with ORCID IDs is moderate and well below Scopus
469 Author ID and ResearcherID, but much higher than Google Scholar Profile.

470 A gender gap exists, with men having more ORCID registrations and being more committed to
471 completing their profiles than women. Profile creation was initially driven by men during the
472 early years after ORCID's introduction. While empirical evidence on this phenomenon is still
473 lacking, gender differences were also observed in Google Scholar profiles, and both researcher
474 profile systems share the requirement of manual account creation. Thus, more empirical support
475 is needed to understand whether this is a common phenomenon or an anomaly in academia, as
476 well as its causes, to address it. This phenomenon could be interpreted through the lens of the
477 Matilda Effect (Rossiter, 1993), which highlights the systemic underrecognition of women in
478 science. Women are often underrepresented in senior academic positions and receive fewer
479 citations even when publishing in top journals (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023). These disparities
480 may discourage them from investing time in maintaining their digital identifiers, particularly
481 when visibility does not translate into equitable recognition or career advancement.

482 Academic hierarchy explains the adoption of ORCID among CSIC staff. As the scientific
483 responsibility increases, so does the proportion of ORCID profiles. Permanent researchers
484 publish consistently. Meanwhile, temporary staff, consisting of predoctoral or postdoctoral
485 researchers, need to publish articles to make their scientific output visible, whereas support
486 staff, mainly composed of technicians, focus their work on service, instrumentation, and
487 management. This can likely be explained not only by job position but also by the number of
488 publications, as many journals require ORCID IDs for publication. Likewise, the employment
489 categories followed an ascending order in terms of completeness, according to their level of
490 scientific involvement, although the percentage of completed fields was low in all cases.
491 Additionally, CSIC-affiliated authors tend to prioritize completing fields that showcase their
492 scientific output, professional and educational background, and linking their profiles to other
493 identifiers. This lack of completion in some cases makes it difficult to uniquely identify authors
494 publishing under the same name, regardless of their institutional affiliation, as they do not
495 always fill out these fields consistently. An incomplete profile not only hinders funding
496 agencies, repositories, or evaluation processes from automating workflows and validating
497 researchers' identities but also prevents bibliometric studies from enriching their research with
498 valuable information.

499 *Maximizing the Benefits of ORCID: Recommendations for Institutions and Researchers*

500 ORCID is more than a technical identifier: it is a strategic tool that secures attribution,
501 strengthens research visibility, and builds trust in scholarly communication. Its integration with
502 editorial, funding, and institutional systems reduces administrative burden and improves
503 metadata quality, while complete and regularly updated researcher profiles amplify individual
504 and institutional recognition. To fully harness these benefits, we recommend the following
505 actions.

506 For institutions (e.g., CSIC): (1) Consolidate ORCID integration with institutional CRIS
507 platforms and funder workflows to streamline reporting, ensure data interoperability, and
508 enhance institutional reputation through trustworthy metadata; (2) Promote researcher
509 authorization for automatic synchronization of publication lists, ensuring that outputs are
510 consistently attributed while reducing manual reporting tasks; (3) Provide targeted training and
511 onboarding for early-career researchers and support staff, highlighting how ORCID can
512 simplify career tracking, support open-science practices, and improve the visibility of diverse
513 research contributions; (4) Monitor ORCID uptake and profile completeness by gender,

514 discipline, and job category, and design interventions to close adoption gaps. This strengthens
515 inclusivity and equity in research evaluation; (5) Position ORCID as a core component of open
516 science infrastructure, demonstrating its value for transparency, interoperability, and the
517 institution's global impact.

518 For researchers: (1) Register and maintain an ORCID iD as a professional asset that guarantees
519 correct attribution across name changes, multiple affiliations, and different languages; (2) Keep
520 key fields updated—Works, Employment, and Education—since profile completeness directly
521 enhances discoverability, supports funding applications, and ensures recognition of all types of
522 outputs, from datasets and software to articles and creative works; (3) Enable automatic imports
523 from publishers, repositories, and funders to reduce administrative effort while ensuring that
524 records remain accurate and comprehensive; (4) Use ORCID proactively on CVs, institutional
525 profiles, and grant applications to strengthen academic visibility and signal alignment with
526 international open-science standards.

527 In short, widespread and active ORCID adoption benefits both researchers and institutions:
528 researchers gain visibility, recognition, and reduced administrative workload, while institutions
529 obtain accurate, interoperable, and trusted metadata to support reporting, evaluation, and
530 strategic planning. Promoting ORCID and encouraging the completion of researcher profiles is
531 therefore not only a matter of compliance but also a pathway to greater transparency, efficiency,
532 and global impact.

533 We hope this study provides valuable insights for CSIC to optimize the adoption and use of
534 ORCID among its researchers. Understanding adoption patterns and metadata completeness will
535 enable CSIC to develop targeted strategies for encouraging the use of ORCID and other
536 persistent identifiers. Moreover, this research highlights the need for greater standardization and
537 data practices, which can contribute to enhancing the visibility and impact of CSIC's research
538 outputs on a national and international scale. By addressing gender disparities and job category
539 differences in ORCID adoption, the findings could help guide future institutional policies and
540 support actions aimed at improving the overall research environment within CSIC. Ultimately,
541 the results may contribute to a more efficient and integrated research management system,
542 fostering a stronger commitment to open science principles and enhancing CSIC's role in the
543 global research community.

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553 **8. References**

- 554 Abalkina, A. (2024). Challenges posed by hijacked journals in Scopus. *Journal of the*
555 *Association for Information Science and Technology*, 75(4), 395–422.
556 <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24855>
- 557 Aghassibake, N., Castello, O. G., Gujilde, P., & Rabun, S. (2023). Visualizing institutional
558 activity using persistent identifier metadata. *Information Services and Use*, 43(3–4),
559 335–342. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-230218>
- 560 Arroyo-Machado, W., Vargas-Quesada, B., Muñoz-Écija, T., & Chinchilla-Rodríguez, Z.
561 (2025). Exploring ORCID adoption and metadata presence in Spain’s research
562 landscape. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-025-05248-8>
- 563 Boudry, C., & Bouchard, A. (2025). Adoption and use of author identifier services: A French
564 national survey. *Learned Publishing*, e1640. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1640>
- 565 Boudry, C., & Durand-Barthez, M. (2020). Use of author identifier services (ORCID,
566 ResearcherID) and academic social networks (Academia.edu, ResearchGate) by the
567 researchers of the University of Caen Normandy (France): A case study. *PLoS ONE*,
568 15(9): e0238583. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238583>
- 569 Calvo, B. S., & Arquero Avilés, R. (2020). Plataformas digitales y reputación académica:
570 análisis del área de Biblioteconomía y Documentación en España. *Ibersid: Revista De*
571 *Sistemas De información Y documentación*, 14(1), 69–77.
572 <https://doi.org/10.54886/ibersid.v14i1.4692>
- 573 Candal-Pedreira, C., Ruano-Ravina, A., Pérez-Ríos, M., & Provencio, M. (2024). Promoting
574 responsible scientific research: integrating retractions into the ORCID profile. *Journal*
575 *of Clinical Epidemiology*, 172, 111403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111403>
- 576 Choraś, M., & Jaroszewska-Choraś, D. (2020). The scrutinizing look on the impending
577 proliferation of mandatory ORCID use from the perspective of data protection, privacy
578 and freedom of science. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, 45(4), 492–507.
579 <https://doi.org/10.1080/03080188.2020.1780773>
- 580 Costas, R., Corona-Sobrino, C., & Robinson-García, N. (2024). Could ORCID play a key role
581 in meta-research? Discussing new analytical possibilities to study the dynamics of
582 science and scientists. In A. Oancea, G. E. Derrick, N. Nuseibeh & X. Xu (Eds.),
583 *Handbook of Meta-Research* (pp. 215–232). Edward Elgar
584 Publishing <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839105722.00026>
- 585 Cousijn, H., Braukmann, R., Fenner, M., Ferguson, C., van Horik, R., Lammey, R., Meadows,
586 A., & Lambert, S. (2021). Connected research: The potential of the PID graph. *Patterns*,
587 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2020.100180>
- 588 Craft, A. R. (2020). Managing researcher identity: Tools for researchers and librarians. *Serials*
589 *Review*, 46(1), 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2020.1720897>
- 590 Dorado, L. (2019). *ORCID en CSIC: Ventajas de una integración institucional* (Version 1).
591 ORCID. <https://doi.org/10.23640/07243.11213969.v1>

- 592 Fernández-Marcial, V., González-Solar, L., & Vale, A. (2023). Is ORCID your ID? A case
593 study at the Faculty of Arts and Humanities of the University of Porto. *Learned*
594 *Publishing*, 36, 564–576. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1562>
- 595 Fernández-Ramos, A., & Barrionuevo, L. (2021). La difusión de la producción científica en el
596 ámbito de las Humanidades: el caso de la Universidad de León. *Investigación*
597 *Bibliotecológica: Archivonomía, bibliotecología e información*, 36(90), 47-65.
598 <https://doi.org/10.22201/iibi.24488321xe.2022.90.58486>
- 599 Fuhr, J., & Monnin, C. (2024). Researcher profile system adoption and use across discipline and
600 rank: A case study at the University of Manitoba. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 5(3),
601 573-592. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00319
- 602 Gomez, C. J., Herman, A. C., & Parigi, P. (2020). Moving more, but closer: Mapping the
603 growing regionalization of global scientific mobility using ORCID. *Journal of*
604 *Informetrics*, 14(3), 101044. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2020.101044>
- 605 Haak, L.L., Fenner, M., Paglione, L., Pentz, E., & Ratner, H. (2012). ORCID: a system to
606 uniquely identify researchers. *Learned publishing*, 25(4), 259-264.
607 <https://doi.org/10.1087/20120404>
- 608 Hannak, A., Joseph, K., Larremore, D. B., & Cimpian, A. (2023). Field-specific ability beliefs
609 as an explanation for gender differences in academics' career trajectories: Evidence
610 from public profiles on ORCID.Org. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*,
611 125(4), 681-698. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspa0000348>
- 612 Heusse, M.-D., & Cabanac, G. (2022), ORCID growth and field-wise dynamics of adoption: A
613 case study of the Toulouse scientific area. *Learned Publishing*, 35, 454-466.
614 <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1451>
- 615 Houghton, F., & Foster, A. (2024). Resistance and power in Irish higher education: ORCID and
616 the monitored university. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2), 102853.
617 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102853>
- 618 Kim, H. (2025). Global mobility of the recent STEM postdoctoral workforce registered in
619 ORCID. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 6, 119–130. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00341
- 620 Larrieu, M., Boczoń, K., & Beau-Reder, J. (2024, May 29). How many UGA researchers have
621 an ORCID? *Blog du pool d'ingénieurs*. [https://gates-data-shs.gricad-pages.univ-](https://gates-data-shs.gricad-pages.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/blog/en/2024-05-29/ORCID-UGA-exploration)
622 [grenoble-alpes.fr/blog/en/2024-05-29/ORCID-UGA-exploration](https://gates-data-shs.gricad-pages.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/blog/en/2024-05-29/ORCID-UGA-exploration)
- 623 Marín-Arraiza, P. (2019). ORCID in the open science scenario: opportunities for academic
624 libraries. *Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und*
625 *Bibliothekare*, 72(2), 478-493. <https://doi.org/10.31263/voebm.v72i2.2811>
- 626 Marín-Arraiza, P. (2022). Madurez de sistemas de identificadores persistentes: Oportunidades
627 en el contexto español. *Anuario ThinkEPI*, 16.
628 <https://doi.org/10.3145/thinkepi.2022.e16a06>

- 629 Marín-Arraiza, P., & Mejias, G. (2020). Identificadores persistentes: La adopción del orcid iD
630 en España. *Anuario ThinkEPI*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3145/thinkepi.2020.e14e06>
- 631 Moreno-Delgado, A., Cárdenas-Bonett, M., De Gregorio-Vicente, Ó., & Montero-Díaz, J.
632 (2024). Mapping scientific mobility in leading Eurozone economies: Insights from
633 ORCID data analysis. *Scientometrics*, 129, 6889–6907. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-05153-6)
634 [024-05153-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-05153-6)
- 635 Morgan, M., & Eichenlaub, N. (2018). Author identifier analysis: Name authority control in two
636 institutional repositories. *International Conference on Dublin Core and Metadata*
637 *Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.23106/dcmi.952139036>
- 638 ORCID (2025). *ORCID Record Schema*. [https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-](https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-guide/orcid-record)
639 [guide/orcid-record](https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-guide/orcid-record)
- 640 Pampel, H., Schrader, A. C., Vierkant, P., Dreyer, B., Glagla-Dietz, S., Schirrwagen, J., &
641 Summann, F. (2024). Lessons learned from ORCID DE—A project-driven initiative to
642 promote author identification in Germany. *Learned Publishing*, 37, 117-124.
643 <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1597>
- 644 Porter, S. J. (2022). Measuring research information citizenship across ORCID practice.
645 *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 7, 779097.
646 <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2022.779097>
- 647 Quinn, A. M. (2023). Promoting ORCID registration at Emory University's school of law. *The*
648 *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 49(6), 102656.
649 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102656>
- 650 Rossiter, M. W. (1993). The Matthew Matilda effect in science. *Social Studies of Science*, 23(2),
651 325–341. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631293023002004>
- 652 Sixto-Costoya, A., Robinson-Garcia, N., Van Leeuwen, T., & Costas, R. (2021). Exploring the
653 relevance of ORCID as a source of study of data sharing activities at the individual-
654 level: A methodological discussion. *Scientometrics*, 126(8), 7149–7165.
655 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04043-5>
- 656 Sugimoto, C. R., & Larivière, V. (2023). *Equity for women in science: Dismantling systemic*
657 *barriers to advancement*. Harvard University Press.
- 658 Teixeira da Silva, J. A. (2020). ORCID: Issues and concerns about its use for academic
659 purposes and research integrity. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 67(4), 246-
660 250.
661 [http://op.niscpr.res.in/index.php/ALIS/article/view/36267#:~:text=10.56042/alis.v67i4.](http://op.niscpr.res.in/index.php/ALIS/article/view/36267#:~:text=10.56042/alis.v67i4.36267)
662 [36267](http://op.niscpr.res.in/index.php/ALIS/article/view/36267#:~:text=10.56042/alis.v67i4.36267)
- 663 Teixeira da Silva, J. A. (2024). Discontinuity between journals' registration and submission
664 requirements for Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID). *Nurse Author &*
665 *Editor*, 34(2), e12061. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nae2.12061>

- 666 Tran, C., & Lyon, J. (2017). Faculty use of author identifiers and researcher networking tools.
667 *College & Research Libraries*, 78(2), 171. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.78.2.171>
- 668 Willinsky, J., & Pimentel, D. (2024). The publication facts label: A public and professional
669 guide for research articles. *Learned Publishing*, 37(2), 139-146.
670 <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1599>
- 671 Xu, S. B., & Hu, G. (2024). Rethinking the author name ambiguity problem and beyond: the
672 case of the Chinese context. *Accountability in Research*, 1–24.
673 <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2349115>
- 674 Yan, E., Zhu, Y., & He, J. (2020). Analyzing academic mobility of US professors based on
675 ORCID data and the Carnegie Classification. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(4), 1451-
676 1467. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00088
- 677 Zhang, L., & Kumaran, M. (2022). STEM Librarians' Presence on Academic Profile Websites.
678 *Science & Technology Libraries*, 42(2), 247-263.
679 <https://doi.org/10.1080/0194262X.2022.2049954>
- 680 Zhang, L., & Li, C. (2020). Investigating Science Researchers' Presence on Academic Profile
681 Websites: A Case Study of a Canadian Research University. *Issues In Science And
682 Technology Librarianship*, 95. <https://doi.org/10.29173/istl51>

683 **Declarations**

684 **Data availability statement**

685 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at
686 <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17321870>.

687 **Conflict of interest**

688 Authors have no conflict of interest relevant to this article.

689 **Declaration of AI**

690 The authors utilized ChatGPT (GPT-4) to review the manuscript, enhancing clarity and fluency
691 while correcting grammatical errors.